

Anton O. OVCHAROV,

*Kazan Innovative University named after V. G. Timiryasov (Kazan, Russia),
Russian State University of Justice (Moscow, Russia);
PhD (Dr. Sc.) in Economics, Professor; e-mail: anton19742006@yandex.ru*

Ildar S. KABIROV,

*Kazan Innovative University named after V. G. Timiryasov (Kazan, Russia);
PhD (Cand. Sc.) in Economics, Associate Professor; e-mail: 55505_05@mail.ru*

TOURISM IN SMALL TOWNS OF RUSSIA: FEATURES AND ASSESSMENTS

Abstract. *The objective of the study is to describe the place and role of small towns in the tourism potential of the Russian Federation. A review of the literature on the current state and prospects for tourism development in small Russian towns is conducted. The study identifies the types of tourism that act as drivers of regional development in modern conditions. In particular, the prospects of estate and ecological tourism for small towns are substantiated. It is concluded that the main problem is the differences in tourism infrastructure and the unevenness of tourist activity in different territories. Quantitative assessments of this unevenness were obtained through the development and implementation of the author's index. A comprehensive statistical database was compiled, reflecting tourist activity in a sample of small towns located in different regions of the Russian Federation. On this basis, groups of statistical indicators were formed and used to construct the index. The methodology for constructing the index was an advanced statistical tool – the principal component analysis. The calculation results made it possible to build a rating of small towns in Russia according to the level of their tourism development. The leaders of the rating in 2023 were Suzdal, Yelabuga, Uglich, and the outsiders were Gavrilov Posad, Sarapul, Irbit. An analysis of changes in the index values for the period from 2019 to 2023 was conducted. The findings indicate that there were no structural shifts significant enough to cause a reordering of towns in the ranking.*

Keywords: *tourism, small towns, infrastructure, index method, statistical indicators, rating*

For citation: Ovcharov, A. O., Kabirov, I. S. (2025). Tourism in small towns of Russia: features and assessments. *Servis v Rossii i za rubezhom [Services in Russia and Abroad]*, 19(1), 5–13. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17130391.

Article History

Received:

Accepted: 2025/05/12.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest
was reported by the author(s).

© 2024 the Author(s)

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0).

To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

УДК 338.48

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17130391

ОВЧАРОВ Антон Олегович,

*Казанский инновационный университет им. В. Г. Тимирязова (Казань, РФ),
Российский государственный университет правосудия (Москва, РФ);
Доктор экономических наук, профессор; e-mail: anton19742006@yandex.ru*

КАБИРОВ Ильдар Сарварович,

*Казанский инновационный университет им. В. Г. Тимирязова (Казань, РФ);
Кандидат экономических наук, доцент; e-mail: 55505_05@mail.ru*

ТУРИЗМ В МАЛЫХ ГОРОДАХ РОССИИ: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И ОЦЕНКИ

Цель исследования заключалась в описании места и роли, которую занимают малые города в туристском потенциале РФ. Обобщена литература по современному состоянию и перспективам развития туризма в малых российских городах. Выделены виды туризма, которые в современных условиях выступают драйвером регионального развития. В частности, для малых городов обоснована перспективность усадебного и экологического туризма. Сделан вывод, что основной проблемой являются различия в туристской инфраструктуре и неравномерность туристской активности на разных территориях. Получены количественные оценки этой неравномерности благодаря разработке и реализации авторского индекса. Собрана обширная статистическая база, отражающая туристскую деятельность по выборке из малых городов, расположенных в разных регионах РФ. На этой основе сформированы группы статистических показателей, которые использовались для конструирования индекса. Методология построения индекса представляла собой продвинутый статистический инструмент – метод главных компонент. Результаты расчетов позволили построить рейтинг малых городов России по уровню их туристского развития. Лидерами рейтинга в 2023 г. стали Суздаль, Елабуга, Углич, а аутсайдерами – Гаврилов Посад, Сарапул, Ирбит. Проведен анализ изменений значений индекса за период 2019–2023 гг. Сделан вывод, что структурных сдвигов, приводящих к перегруппировке малых городов в рейтинге, не наблюдалось.

Ключевые слова: туризм, малые города, инфраструктура, индексный метод, статистические показатели, рейтинг

Для цитирования: Овчаров, А. О., Кабиров, И. С. (2025). Туризм в малых городах России: особенности и оценки. Сервис в России и за рубежом, 19(1), 5–13. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17130391.

Получено:

Одобрено: 12.05.2025.

Introduction

Domestic tourism has currently become a priority sector of tourism in Russia. Its accelerated growth was influenced by many restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and anti-Russian sanctions. As a result, domestic tourism is now considered one of the most promising areas for the development of many Russian regions, including small towns.

At the moment, two opposing approaches have emerged in the Russian academic community in assessing the role and significance of small towns in the development of Russia. The first emphasizes the assertion of the unconditional significance and prospects of a small town as the most important element of the socio-spatial structure of the state. Proponents of the second approach regard most small towns to be economically inefficient and therefore unpromising. According to these scholars, large metropolitan areas should become the main points of economic growth for the country. However, this critical and pessimistic assessment of small towns contradicts the demand for many territories. The small spaces of a small town create favorable conditions for both everyday life and travel.

Small towns tend to experience active development when they become attractive to tourists. Tourism based on the rich natural and historical-cultural heritage of small towns contributes to the sustainable development of territories. Nevertheless, at present, small towns face numerous challenges and problems that hinder the development of tourism. In this article, based on a literature review, we highlight some of them and identify the types of tourism most suitable for small Russian towns. In addition, we demonstrate the content and results of our own empirical research aimed at obtaining specific assessments regarding the main problem of tourism in small towns – the unevenness of its development.

Tourism in small towns in Russia: literature review

For a long time, small towns in Russia received insufficient attention both in terms of their socio-economic development and their tourism-related activity and attractiveness. However, recent years

have seen the emergence of fundamental scientific works that examine the most pressing problems of small town development, develop concepts of the social space of a modern small town, and substantiate strategies for the socio-economic and socio-cultural development of various types of small towns (see, for example, [2; 3; 5]).

Small towns have always been the most common type of urban settlements in Russia. At present, Russia has over 1,100 cities, approximately 70 % of which are cities with a population of less than 50 thousand people, i.e. small towns. In geopolitical terms, small towns hold together the vast expanses of Russia, thereby ensuring its integrity. They are an important component of the country's socio-economic structure and play an important role in preserving cultural heritage. At the same time, small towns face considerable problems in the areas of demography, economics, social policy, and infrastructure. These challenges include declining birth rates and the outflow of population from small towns, inequality in access to education, medicine, comfortable housing conditions, low investment attractiveness, etc. The challenges facing small towns actualize the search for ways to help them overcome the crisis and negative trends in the socio-economic and socio-cultural spheres.

As suggested by many experts, one of these ways could be to increase the importance of tourism in small towns. Thus, against the background of the depressive state of small towns, the attention of researchers is drawn to issues of long-term strategy. In this context, individual trajectories for the development of various types of tourism are often proposed. These trajectories take into account local specificities, which may serve as a specific growth point for a particular territory [15].

Nevertheless, not all scholars consider local tourism to be a significant factor capable of bringing small towns to a qualitatively new level of development. According to some experts, only cities with a rich historical and cultural heritage possess genuine tourist potential. Furthermore, the growth of tourist flow does not necessarily guarantee a resolution of urban problems,

but can destroy the unique socio-cultural landscape of a small town [16].

Small towns possess significant natural resource and historical-cultural potential, due to which the functioning of the tourism industry is possible. More than half of the small Russian towns have the state status of “historical cities”. Within their boundaries are the objects of outstanding historical and cultural value (archaeological, architectural and urban planning, aesthetic, scientific, etc.). This indicates the presence of favorable prerequisites for the development of tourism. In many cases, the tourism industry can become a significant source of financial revenues to local budgets and contribute to positive changes in the life of small towns. Forming a competent marketing strategy is one of the ways to increase the tourist attractiveness of a city. To create a competitive tourism product, it is necessary to work on improving tourism marketing and modern marketing practices. Such work was carried out, for example, in the form of creating a tourism product for small towns in the Tula and Vladimir regions, as well as the Perm Territory [14]. A vital element of the marketing strategy is information support for the tourist opportunities of a small town, as well as the implementation of a competent image policy to create a positive image of the locality. The most effective direction of information policy is the formation of a territorial brand that creates a positive image of the settlement and helps to attract tourists. Thus, the results of a survey of the administrations of a number of small towns demonstrated that the most common answer to the question about the purpose of creating a brand, in addition to increasing recognition and creating a certain image of the city, was also an increase in tourist flow. More than half of the respondents answered affirmatively to the question about the positive effect of branding [8].

Obviously, some specific types of tourism should become the driver of tourism development in small towns. One of them is estate tourism. The presence of old estates in small towns as a special object of cultural heritage motivates tourists

to travel, meets the request to get to know a special phenomenon of Russian history and culture better. Not many works have been written on the topic of estate tourism in small towns. The main part of the research is devoted to general issues of estate tourism: the history of the emergence of noble estates, the architecture of their buildings, landscape design, interiors, traditions and lifestyle of the families living in the estates. In the context of the subject of our article, it is worth noting the work that examines the current state of estate tourism in the regions [13]. The work identifies problems and prospects for the development of estate tourism, and provides recommendations for improving tourism activities in the field of estate complexes.

In addition to estate tourism, ecological tourism can also play a positive role for small towns. Many small settlements have unique and diverse natural resources that create the prerequisites for the development of this type of tourism. The establishment of recreational areas and ecotourism within specially protected natural areas located near small towns is one of the aspects in the sustainable development of small towns. The creation of not only natural, but also new historical and cultural tourist routes and guided tours contributes to the prospect of sustainable development of small towns. Thus, one of the projects of the tourist route involves the unification of small towns of the Volga region into a tourist and recreational cluster [1]. This initiative is intended to help revive historically significant small towns in the Volga region of Russia that possess rich cultural heritage.

The revitalization of the cultural and historical heritage also plays a crucial role in the shaping a type of tourism that is considered both new and promising – so-called “creative tourism”. This type of tourism marks a transition from the traditional passive model of providing tourist services to the active participation of tourists in various events (festivals, seminars, master classes, etc.). Creative tourism can become a comprehensive strategy for small-town development. Key factors in attracting tourists within the framework of this strategy include creative elements such as immersion, participation, interactivity and other

features that contribute to the creation of innovative tourism products. In general, creative tourism has the potential to improve the image and increase the competitiveness of the territory, as well as mitigate the seasonal unevenness of tourist demand [6].

It should be noted that the development of small towns implies the creation of a comfortable urban environment and public spaces that contribute to improving the quality of life and foster active engagement among both residents and visitors. However, the current state of the urban environment of small historical towns in Russia is often rated as unattractive. Outdated infrastructure, dilapidated or semi-ruined cultural heritage sites create a negative impression for tourists. With high-quality restoration and competent marketing, they could be added to the list of cultural heritage sites and activate the organization of cultural, educational, event-based, and other tourism routes. This, in turn, could help attract both domestic and international tourists to these towns.

Tourist attractiveness can be improved by placing greater emphasis on the development of tourism infrastructure. According to many experts, it is the underdeveloped infrastructure that is the main factor holding back the development of tourism in Russia [4]. The deterioration of utility, transport and energy systems, the slow pace of development in accommodation and food services, and the generally low quality of services pose significant barriers to the effective development of tourism in small towns.

At the same time, there are signs of positive dynamics, as the state invests significant funds in Russian tourism through federal and regional support programs. However, such support is not provided everywhere, but rather selectively. As a result, Russia exhibits territorial disparities in tourism infrastructure, which in turn lead to uneven tourism development across the country. Many researches point to this problem – they highlight the causes and factors, propose assessment indicators, formulate recommendations for overcoming regional imbalances (see, for example, [9; 11]). This issue of disparity is also present

among small towns and clearly requires in-depth academic investigation.

In the empirical part of this article, we will present our own assessments of the uneven development of small towns. These assessments will be based on the construction, calculation, and interpretation of a specialized metric – the small town tourism development index.

Thus, the presented literary review presented the multifaceted nature of the topic of tourism in relation to small towns in Russia. It also allowed us to outline promising areas for the development and activation of tourism in small towns.

Data and methodology

In the empirical part of the article, we set the task of obtaining comparative assessments characterizing the level of tourism development in small towns across Russia. This was achieved through the collection and processing of tourism-related indicators. Moreover, we chose not to obtain assessments using private indicators, but did instead constructed a composite indicator (index).

It is worth noting that the index method is widely used in tourism research. Most commonly, it is applied in the analysis of tourism competitiveness in the context of countries and regions. For example, the well-known Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Index (TTCI) is used annually to rank countries based on their tourism activity. Other examples include various types of climate indices, which help evaluate the climatic appeal of tourist destinations in different regions. One such example is the **Camping Climate Index**, which allows for the assessment of how weather conditions influence campsite occupancy rates [7].

At the same time, the index method is rarely used to study tourism in small towns in Russia. We can only highlight the study [10], in which the tourist attractiveness of small and medium-sized towns in the Perm Territory was assessed using a special index. This index was obtained by aggregating 30 individual indicators, the information for which was collected at the expert level in the municipalities of the region.

In our study, we excluded the subjectivity of gathering information on tourism data. The

database was compiled exclusively from Rosstat indicators, reflecting the dynamics of tourism in small towns of the Russian Federation from different sides. The initial dataset was based on a sample of 8 small towns, with preliminary calculations previously presented at an international conference [12]. However, for the purposes of this article, the sample was expanded to 12 cities, all members of the Association of Small Tourist Cities of Russia. To ensure territorial representation, the sampling followed the principle of one small town per federal subject of the Russian Federation. Moreover, we took into account the limits of municipal-level statistics, selecting towns for which the most complete statistical data could be collected.

For calculations and subsequent analysis, the period 2019–2023 was covered. All Rosstat data were divided into 6 groups of indicators (27 individual indicators in total), directly or indirectly related to tourism (Table 1). Indirect accounting must be done, since the use of exclusively direct indicators can distort the result, leading to unreliable estimates. For example, excluding traffic accident indicators means that the tourism safety factor, which can affect tourist activity, is not taken into account.

The index calculation methodology itself is based on the principal component analysis method, which allows for the aggregation of the collected data with minimal loss of the original information. In essence, our index is the first principal component (PC_1), which presents the main

information about tourism in a small town. It is determined by the formula:

$$PC_{1i} = \sum_{j=1}^p u_{j1} \cdot \left(\frac{\tilde{X}_{ji} - \bar{\tilde{X}}_j}{S_{\tilde{X}_j}} \right),$$

where \tilde{X}_{ji} is the value of the j -th variable for the i -th object (city), $\bar{\tilde{X}}_j$ is the average value of the j -th variable (a specific indicator from Table 1); $S_{\tilde{X}_j}$ is the estimate of the standard deviation of the j -th variable; u_{j1} is the factor loading of the first principal component on the j -th variable.

Results

The results of calculations performed using the econometric software EViews for the selected data array made it possible to form a model of the tourism development index for each year. For example, for 2023 it looks like:

$$PC_1 = 0.021\tilde{X}_1 + 0.373\tilde{X}_2 + 0.250\tilde{X}_3 + \dots \\ \dots + 0.139\tilde{X}_{26} + 0.217\tilde{X}_{27}.$$

Converting into a scale that is easy to understand (from 0 to 100 %) made it possible to obtain index assessments for all 12 selected small towns (Fig. 1).

The obtained results confirm the conclusions of many researchers regarding the unevenness of regional tourism. Today, a kind of “pool” of regions has developed in the Russian Federation, where the main tourist infrastructure is concentrated and where there is a high demand for tourist services (Moscow, St. Petersburg, the Republic of Tatarstan, and several others). The same can be said about small

Table 1 – Selection of indicators for index construction

Group name	Indicators description	Number of indicators
Tourist flow and tour operators	Data on Russian and foreign tourists, tour operators, agencies, and the sales of tours to small towns	6
Accommodation facilities	Hotels and other accommodation facilities data: number, room capacity, number of guests, etc.	5
Tourist services	Data on paid services provided to the population, public catering facilities and their turnover	4
Transport and roads	Passenger turnover, road length and number of gas stations data	4
Tourists resources	Museums, natural, cultural and archaeological sites data	4
Tourism safety	Road accidents, number of victims and reported crimes data	4

Fig. 1 – Index of tourism development of small towns in Russia in 2023

Table 2 – Rating of tourism development of small towns in Russia for 2019–2023

City	Index value (ranking position)					Change in points (position) in the ranking (+/-) in 2023 vs. 2019
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	
Suzdal (Vladimir region)	77.2 (1)	67.9 (1)	78.1 (1)	85.3 (1)	87.6 (1)	+10.4 (no change)
Elabuga (Republic of Tatarstan)	69.8 (3)	63.5 (2)	75.0 (3)	81.9 (2)	79.9 (2)	+10.1 (moved up 1 position)
Uglich (Yaroslavl region)	72.4 (2)	60.9 (3)	78.3 (2)	80.1 (3)	76.1 (3)	+3.7 (dropped 1 position)
Tobolsk (Tyumen region)	62.7 (4)	56.4 (4)	68.9 (4)	69.4 (4)	70.7 (4)	+13.2 (no change)
Azov (Rostov region)	56.0 (5)	48.7 (5)	52.4 (5)	60.6 (5)	63.3 (5)	+7.3 (no change)
Solikamsk (Perm krai)	27.3 (6)	19.2 (7)	22.4 (6)	28.0 (7)	31.5 (6)	+4.2 (no change)
Tarusa (Kaluga region)	24.8 (7)	19.7 (6)	21.6 (7)	30.4 (6)	30.8 (7)	+6.0 (no change)
Elets (Lipetsk region)	22.9 (8)	17.5 (8)	20.2 (8)	25.1 (8)	26.4 (8)	+3.5 (no change)
Kargopol (Arkhangel region)	19.5 (9)	15.8 (9)	19.4 (9)	22.3 (9)	23.8 (9)	+4.3 (no change)
Gavrilov Posad (Ivanovo region)	18.6 (10)	13.0 (10)	16.8 (10)	20.3 (10)	22.6 (10)	+6.2 (no change)
Sarapul (Udmurt republic)	12.0 (11)	9.4 (11)	10.8 (12)	14.4 (12)	18.4 (11)	+6.4 (no change)
Irbit (Sverdlovsk region)	10.6 (12)	7.5 (12)	12.1 (11)	15.6 (11)	17.3 (12)	+6.7 (no change)

tourist towns. There are well-known destinations with developed infrastructure and large tourist flows (e. g., Suzdal), and there are small towns with an interesting history and significant tourist potential, which is currently not fully realized. The gaps between the top three and the bottom three are 2–3 times or more, which indicates tourist imbalances.

The final result of the study was the assessment of our index in dynamics. We set the task of checking for structural shifts, i. e. the presence of changes in the detected gaps over time. To do this, we calculated the first principal component, and the resulting index was converted to our scale based on data for 2019–2023. The results are presented in Table 2, which reflects a kind of ranking of the small tourist towns included in our sample.

This table demonstrates that the hypothesis of structural shifts was not confirmed, as there were virtually no changes in the ranking. There was a decrease in the index values in 2020, which can be explained by the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the tourism sector. However, this decline was observed across all small tourist towns and did not lead to a regrouping of positions in the ranking.

Conclusion

The article highlights the relevance and importance of the problem of overcoming the

crisis state of small Russian towns and positioning the trajectory of socio-economic growth. The driver of such growth can be tourism, the potential of which is the natural resource and historical-cultural heritage of small territories.

Based on a review of academic literature, the article demonstrated the main directions of stimulating tourism activities in small towns. Specific types of tourism that have the greatest development potential in municipalities are highlighted. It is concluded that disproportions in regional tourism infrastructure lead to uneven tourism development in small towns.

In order to obtain comparative assessments of tourism development in small towns, the study presents the content and results of an empirical analysis. It was aimed at developing a specific indicator (index) characterizing the unevenness of tourism development in small towns. Based on extensive statistical data and an advanced statistical method, specific quantitative estimates were obtained. In fact, a rating of small towns by the level of tourist activity was created. The leaders of this rating in 2023 were Suzdal, Elabuga, Uglich, and the outsiders were Gavrillov Posad, Sarapul and Irbit. Meanwhile, the dynamic analysis (covering the period 2019–2023) showed that there were no significant changes in this rating over time.

References

1. Butorov, S. A. (2021). Vnutrennij turizm v Rossii: nerealizovannyj potencial [Domestic tourism in Russia: Unrealized potential]. *Vestnik Moskovskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta kul'tury i iskusstv [Bulletin of the Moscow State University of Culture and Arts]*, 3(101), 178–184. doi: 10.24412/1997-0803-2021-3101-178-184. (In Russ.).
2. Chernysh, M. F., et al. (2020). *Prostranstvennoe razvitie malyh gorodov: social'nye strategii i praktiki [Spatial development of small towns: Social strategies and practices]*: monograph. Moscow: Federal Research Sociological Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences. doi: 10.19181/monogr.978-5-89697-335-5.2020. (In Russ.).
3. Chernysh, M. F., et al. (2021). *Malye goroda Rossii: novye vyzovy, social'nye problemy i perspektivy [Small towns of Russia: New challenges, social problems and prospects]*: monograph. Moscow: Federal Research Sociological Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences. doi: 10.19181/monogr.978-5-89697-378-2.2021. (In Russ.).
4. Frolova, E. V., & Kabanova, E. E. (2017). Faktory razvitiya turisticheckoj privlekatel'nosti municipal'nyh obrazovanij Rossii [Factors in the development of tourist attractiveness of municipalities in Russia]. *Voprosy gosudarstvennogo i municipal'nogo upravleniya [Issues of State and Municipal Administration]*, 3, 112–128. (In Russ.).

5. Karbainov, N., et al. (2019). *Malye goroda v social'nom prostranstve Rossii [Small towns in the social space of Russia]: monograph*. Moscow: Federal Research Sociological Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences. doi: 10.19181/monogr.978-5-89697-323-2.2019. (In Russ.).
6. Kvita, G. N., Luchina, N. A., & Arshinova, A. N. (2022). Kreativnyj turizm kak faktor razvitiya rossijskogo turistskogo biznesa [Creative tourism as a factor in the development of Russian tourist business]. *Sovremennaya konkurenciya [Modern competition]*, 16(1), 29–40. doi: 10.37791/2687-0649-2022-16-1-29-40. (In Russ.).
7. Ma, S., Craig, C.A., & Feng, S. (2020). The Camping Climate Index (CCI): The development, validation, and application of a camping-sector tourism climate index. *Tourism Management*, 80, 104105. doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2020.104105.
8. Makarov, P. Yu., Sokolova, M. V., & Illarionov, A. E. (2023). Issledovanie praktiki branding malykh gorodov: vopros' rukovodstvo gorodskikh administratsii [Study of the practice of branding small towns: a survey of the leaders of city administrations]. *Voprosy gosudarstvennogo i municipal'nogo upravleniya [Issues of State and Municipal Administration]*, 1, 66–88. doi: 10.17323/1999-5431-2023-0-1-66-88. (In Russ.).
9. Morozov, M. A., & Morozova, N. S. (2021). Regional'ny'e osobennosti razvitiya turistskoj infrastruktury i ix vliyanie na turizm [Regional features of the development of tourist infrastructure and their influence on tourism]. *Regionologiya [Regionology]*, 29(3), 588–610. doi: 10.15507/2413-1407.116.029.202103.588-610. (In Russ.).
10. Myshlyavtseva, S. E., Merkushev, S. A., & Lanin, V. V. (2023). Metodika ocenki turistskoj privlekatel'nosti malyh i srednih gorodov (na materialah Permskogo kraja) [Assessment procedures for studying the tourist attractiveness of small and medium cities (case study of the Perm region)]. *Vestnik Moskovskogo universiteta. Seriya 5, Geografiya [Lomonosov Geography Journal]*, 5, 52–64. doi: 10.55959/MSU0579-9414.5.78.5.6. (In Russ.).
11. Ovcharov, A. O., & Kabirov, I. S. (2024). Tourism development index of Russian regions. *Servis v Rossii i za rubezhom [Services in Russia and Abroad]*, 18(2), 135–143. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12605923.
12. Ovcharov, A. O., & Kabirov, I. S. (2024). *Indeks turistskogo razvitiya malyh gorodov [Index of tourist development of small towns]. Volgo-Kam'ye: istoriya, social'no-kul'turnoe nasledie i perspektivy [Volga-Kamy: History, Socio-Cultural Heritage and Prospects]: Proceedings of the II Russian Scientific and Practical Conference*. Kazan: Publishing house "Poznaniye" ["Cognition"] of Kazan Innovation University, 17–19. (In Russ.).
13. Pasternak, K. G. (2024). Usadebnyj turizm kak indikator prodvizheniya kul'turno-istoricheskogo naslediya malyh gorodov i sel'skih poselenij [Estate tourism as an indicator of the promotion of the cultural and historical heritage of small towns and rural settlements]. *Moskovskij ekonomicheskij zhurnal [Moscow Economic Journal]*, 9(3), 366–390. doi: 10.55186/2413046X_2024_9_3_154. (In Russ.).
14. Sheresheva, M. Yu., Berezka, S. M., & Oborin, M. S. (2018). Sozdanie turistskogo produkta malyh gorodov [Creating a tourists product in small towns]. *Vestnik Moskovskogo universiteta. Seriya 6, Ekonomika [Moscow University Economics Bulletin]*, 5, 94–112. doi: 10.38050/01300105201855. (In Russ.).
15. Smoleva, E. O., & Kosygina, K. E. (2024). Razvitie malyh gorodov: ot individual'nyh traektorij k strategicheskomu planirovaniyu [Development of small towns: From individual trajectories to strategic planning]. *Ekonomicheskie i social'nye peremeny: fakty, tendencii, prognoz [Economic and Social Changes: Facts, Trends, Forecast]*, 17(5), 169–183. doi: 10.15838/esc.2024.5.95.9. (In Russ.).
16. Velikaya, N. M. (2021). Kul'turnoe razvitie malykh i srednego gorodov Rossii kak faktor sokhraneniya natsional'noi identichnosti [Cultural development of small and medium-sized cities of Russia as a factor in the preservation of national identity]. *Observatoriya kul'tury [Observatory of Culture]*, 18(3), 240–253. doi: 10.25281/2072-3156-2021-18-3-240-253. (In Russ.).